

POLAND

POLAND

THE INFLUENCE OF ECONOMIC THOUGHT ON VALUES

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about human economic activity in society, reliance on the family environment in imparting economic knowledge, economic science, and the role of the educational system in improving literacy.

Keywords: society, culture, economic, thinking, activity, material, human, production, care, process.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация об экономической деятельности человека в обществе, опоре на семейную среду при передаче экономических знаний, экономической науки, а также о роли системы образования в повышении грамотности.

Ключевые слова: общество, культура, экономическое, мышление, деятельность, материальное, человек, производство, забота, процесс.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu makolada jamiyatda inson iqtisodiy faoliyati, iqtisodiy bilimlarni berisda, avalo, oila muhitiga tayanilishi, iktisodii ilm, savodxonlikni oshirishda ta'lim tizimi o'rni haqida ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: jamiyat, madaniyat, iqtisodiy, tafakkur, faoliyat, moddiy, inson, ishlab chiqarish, ehtiyot, jarayon.

Recently, the first fundamental book of the head of our country entitled "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan" was published. When talking about the similar aspect of the Development Strategy, which will be implemented for the next five years, to the Action Strategy, which was implemented in all spheres of the country's life in the past five years, it should be noted that this strategic document was adopted only after a wide public discussion. should be focused.

In society, all material and spiritual goods produced as a result of human economic activity, labor, ultimately aim to provide human consumption and satisfy his needs. In order to satisfy his vital needs, a person works tirelessly and conducts economic activities.

In our opinion, economic development is inextricably linked not only with the production of delicacies, but also with their consumption. Because consumption is the main goal, and production is a means of achieving it. The luxury saved in the consumption process with the help of high economic consciousness and thinking, in its essence, means the amount of additional

product created in the process of production. There is a saying in our people, which comes from long-term practical experience, “find the world, find the account”.

“Eat, drink, but do not waste” inscriptions were written in “Avesta” many centuries ago. Therefore, our people have not been indifferent to the extravagances allowed in the consumption process since time immemorial, they strongly condemned it. A simple formulation of our opinion on waste is as follows: it is better not to produce than to produce and destroy.

In the action strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, in the concepts of national economy development of the Development Strategy for 2022-2026, and other draft laws, opportunities were created to encourage the implementation of this rule. Today, as we are concerned about the economic progress of our country and its further development, we should teach not only the adults, but also our youth, who are the successors of the third renaissance, to master the economic teachings of the above thinkers.[1]

The waste that is allowed in the consumption of delicacies that are as necessary for our daily life as water, created by the hard work of man, especially the losses that occur as a result of the low efficiency of using food resources in luxury restaurants, The role of the consumer economic worldview is very large in eliminating problems such as the low efficiency of use of precious resources such as gas, electricity, and water in households. In this way, we would like to emphasize that today's consumer culture in our country does not meet the requirements of the time due to the narrow scope of economic thinking of our people and the lack of economic knowledge.

Each family is a separate state. It will have its own economic issues and solutions in different directions. Family members with economic knowledge can improve their living conditions and provide a higher income.[2] In this regard, people with insufficient literacy can destroy their existing income, cannot properly distribute material resources, and as a result, they may end up in poverty.

However, in our country, it has become a priority task of the state policy to provide all the conditions for every person to live a comfortable life, to create vacancies in every field, to provide people with a permanent source of income by helping them acquire knowledge, trade, and entrepreneurship. Last year alone, about 200,000 business entities were established and 10,000 enterprises expanded their activities in order to reduce poverty.

Reforms to introduce free market mechanisms, ensure healthy competition and privacy of private property, and support entrepreneurship are reaching a new level. Tax and customs administration is being simplified based on best practices. The value added tax rate has been reduced from 15% to 12% this year. Due to this, it is calculated that at least 14 trillion sums will remain at the disposal of entrepreneurs. Naturally, this money will be directed to the development of business, creation of new jobs and the well-being of workers and, therefore, the population. That is, conditions and opportunities are being created for citizens to get an education, work in decent conditions and earn income. Now it's all about using these opportunities correctly and productively. For this, economic knowledge and skills are necessary.

It is true that the family environment is primarily relied upon to impart this knowledge. But it seems that the educational system has a great role in improving economic science and literacy. Especially in today's era, when New Uzbekistan is considered as an enlightened country where an intellectual nation has been formed, this demand is even more urgent. After all, in our country, our enlightened grandfathers said, "Salvation is in education, salvation is in upbringing, salvation is in knowledge". Because all noble goals are achieved through knowledge and education", a huge investment is being made in improving the quality of education. [3]

When it comes to this, the level of quality coverage of children with preschool education has reached 80%, 600,000 new kindergarten places have been created, the "A-level" educational program approved in 130 countries has been launched in presidential schools, academic and financial independence has been granted to 41 institutes from 198 universities. It is worth noting that the resources for preferential educational loans for students were doubled, and the salary of scientists was increased by 4.5 times.

These efforts will continue consistently. Because improving the quality of education was chosen as the only correct way of development of New Uzbekistan. In this way, a solid foundation is being laid for the education and formation of an intellectual nation capable of creating the Third Renaissance.

In this process, the formation of economic knowledge in the younger generation is becoming one of the educational needs. It is right to start teaching such knowledge from children. That is, the formation of economic thinking, active attitude to socio-economic life of students from a young age, creation of the necessary conditions for raising business-minded, mentally active citizens is the demand of today. [4] The fact is that children quickly and easily adapt to any new

situation. But what about the conditions of the market economy, that is, property relations, which are based on constant changes?

The latest research in this regard requires some updates regarding the definition of the subject of economic psychology. We know that the economy is a complex, multifaceted system, and its essence is often obscure to a young child. This is because children perceive processes specific to different economic models based on their worldview and abilities. [5] They come face to face with completely new economic realities and problems in the process of socio-economic conditions that arise during the gradual transition to the market economy, and realize the need to develop skills for new life conditions. In elucidating the essence of this process, the solution to the problem goes back to the meaning of the concept of “economic socialization”.

In the process of economic socialization, if we observe a high level of the desire of young men to develop themselves in their activities and the motivation to achieve success, the gender policy conducted in our society and the high attention paid to women show that the characteristics of “leadership” are developing in the behavior of our girls. In short, first of all, the views on social life and changes in consciousness in Eastern philosophy serve as an important spiritual heritage, value in deepening the understanding that the implementation of social changes in our lives today is related to economic consciousness. [6]

Due to the professional self-representation and career orientation of the representatives of the mature age generation, due to the correct assessment of themselves and their capabilities, they created the basis for the formation of the system of “social honors - rules of life - attitude towards money” in their children. These skills are similar among young people, and as a result, we can see that young men and women are economically socialized and the level of economic literacy is increasing.

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